

Image: A. Porcher/CEA/DRF/IRFU

ELECTRON & PROTON BEAM TESTING

The Accelerator Research and Innovation for European Science and Society (ARIES) project offers funding for access to 5 European facilities under its Transnational Access scheme.

**A
N
K
A**

ANKA
KIT, Germany

Electrons between 0.5 - 2.5 GeV
Adjustable electron bunch lengths
Operator-defined bunch filling patterns

**F
L
U
T
E**

FLUTE
KIT, Germany

Electron energies of 7 & 40 - 50 MeV
Bunch length range 1 - 300 fs
Charge range from 1 pC - 3 nC/bunch

**I
P
H
I**

IPHI
CEA Paris-Saclay, France

3 MeV protons
Duty cycle 1 ms/1 Hz to 100 mA/CW
Neutron source at low flux
352 MHz RF test facility

**S
I
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B
A
D**

SINBAD
DESY, Germany

Electron bunches of 0.1 - 20 pC
charge to 100 MeV
Bunch length of a few fs
Available as of 2019

**V
E
L
A**

VELA
STFC Daresbury, UK

Electrons of 6 MeV, 10 Hz
Pulses of 100 fs
An upgrade to 40 MeV, 100 Hz is
currently in progress

For more details on the facilities and funding opportunities, please visit:
<https://aries.web.cern.ch/ta>